

Viscosity of electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents

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Viscosities of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 salts in non-aqueous solvents have been measured in the high concentration range at $35.0 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The results have been discussed by using Angell's equation.

There is as yet no satisfactory model of electrolyte solution comparable with the Jones-Dole equation¹, which can explain viscosity increase with concentration in the highly concentrated region. However, the free volume theory² of liquid has been adopted for electrolyte solution which leads to an useful equation for viscosity³,

$$\ln \eta_{\text{rel}} = \frac{k' N}{N_0(N_0 - N)} \quad (1)$$

Experimental results of viscosity measured in large concentration of electrolytes in aqueous solution are available in the literature⁴ and this equation was found to adequately describe the viscosity changes with concentration with suitable choice of N_0 . The two parameters of eq. (1) are k' and N_0 , N_0 is a hypothetical glass transition concentration at the isotherm where the measured relative viscosity $\ln \eta_{\text{rel}}$ at electrolyte concentration N eq. dm^{-3} . However, only limited number of experimental viscosity data of electrolytes in highly concentrated solution in non-aqueous solvents are available in the literature. It was found, however, that even in non-aqueous solvents like *N*-methylformamide (NMF), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), *N*-methylacetamide (NMA), electrolytes both simple^{5,6} and quaternary ammonium halides⁷ follow eq. (1) excellently well. The inorganic salts are appreciably soluble in these solvents and are very suitable for the purpose of testing the validity of eq. (1) in concentrated solution.

A number of spectroscopic studies of lithium salts in *N,N*-dimethylformamide are reported in the literature⁸. These are primarily concerned with solvation effects. Amides as solvents are important in inorganic chemistry. Solvation of salts in amide solvents serves as a model for the binding of salts to peptide groups in protein and polypeptides. Anion solvation in amides is very weak since the amides do not exhibit hydrogen bonding. The solvation of cation through the carboxyl oxygen polarises the molecule and enhances the double bond character of the N-C bond. These considerations prompted us to measure the viscosity of some

common salts, NaBr, KI, ZnCl_2 , $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in solvents, *N,N*-dimethylformamide, *N*-methylformamide and *N*-methylacetamide.

Results and Discussion

The density and relative viscosity data of the 1 : 1 salts NaBr and KI, and 2 : 1 salts ZnCl_2 , $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in amide solvents *N*-methylformamide, *N,N*-dimethylformamide, *N*-methylacetamide are given in Table 1. Normally, the density vs concentration plots are linear even in the high concentration range. However, in the present study, we observe that the density rises rapidly in the high concentration range for ZnCl_2 in DMF and NaBr in NMA. The concentrations of the various salts in different solvents cover the range 0.09–1.3 *N*.

Table 1. Relative viscosity and density of electrolyte in amide solvents at $35.0 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Concentration equiv /lt	Density g cm^{-3}	η_{rel}	Concentration equiv /lt	Density g cm^{-3}	η_{rel}
Solvent NMF					
ZnCl_2			$\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$		
0.69271	1.0227	1.2108	0.33261	1.0029	1.2335
0.27708	1.0025	1.0725	0.26609	1.0004	1.1861
0.19950	0.9991	1.0480	0.21287	0.9987	1.1456
0.15960	0.9973	1.0380	0.17039	0.9975	1.1110
0.12768	0.9960	1.0130	0.13624	0.9957	1.0861
Solvent DMF					
NaBr			KI		
0.68848	0.9803	1.4383	0.42860	0.9922	1.3337
0.41722	0.9623	1.2199	0.34288	0.9803	1.2477
0.25033	0.9505	1.1136	0.27430	0.9711	1.1900
0.15020	0.9427	1.0638	0.21944	0.9654	1.1481
0.09012	0.9370	1.0369	0.17555	0.9611	1.1178
			0.14044	0.9580	1.0943
ZnCl_2			$\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$		
1.39120	1.0078	1.5394	0.41618	0.9764	1.9344
0.83470	0.9779	1.1993	0.31448	0.9661	1.6352
0.50083	0.9603	1.0832	0.23710	0.9582	1.4108
0.30050	0.9496	1.0435	0.16906	0.9513	0.2734
0.18030	0.9492	1.0251	0.13999	0.9483	1.2102

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Table-1 (contd.)

Pb(NO ₃) ₂		Solvent NMA :			
0.22216	0.9661	1.0395			
0.17773	0.9598	1.0230			
0.14218	0.9547	1.0152			
0.11375	0.9512	1.0106			
0.09100	0.9483	1.0082			
	NaBr		KI		
0.49029	0.9751	1.3412	0.22276	0.9751	1.1739
0.39218	0.9696	1.2558	0.17821	0.9699	1.1377
0.31374	0.9661	1.2027	0.14256	0.9657	1.1078
0.25099	0.9639	1.1548	0.11405	0.9630	1.00858
0.20080	0.9623	1.1181	0.09124	0.9611	1.0677
0.16064	0.9613	1.0929			

It may be noted the ZnCl₂ is exceptionally soluble in NMF and DMF compared to the other electrolytes in these solvents. This suggests strong solvation of Zn²⁺ with the carboxyl oxygen of the amides thus polarising the molecule and enhancing the double bond character of the N-C bond. Spectroscopic studies of lithium chloride in DMF also suggest solvation effect.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\ln \eta_{rel}$ vs $N/(N_0 - N)$ for ZnCl₂ in (O) NMF and (Δ) DMF at 35.0 ± 0.05°.

We have plotted $\ln \eta_{rel}$ vs $N/(N_0 - N)$ for a suitable choice of N_0 in order to test the validity of eq. (1) for the salts in amide solvents. The values of N_0 and k' are selected by a trial method⁵. Linearity of the plots observed for all the salts in these solvents, indicates that eq. (1) describes viscosity dependence of electrolyte solution in the concentration region beyond 0.1 M. This is illustrated in Fig. 1 for typical 2 : 1 electrolyte. In Table 2 are given the values of N_0 and fk'/N_0^2 . Previously it was observed that the values of fk'/N_0^2 compare favourably with Jones-Dole B-coefficient. In the present study, we find that the values fk'/N_0^2 are low compared to the literature values of Jones-Dole B-coefficient for NaBr and KI in NMA.

Table 2. Values of N_0 and fk'/N_0^2

Solvent	Electrolyte	N_0	fk'/N_0^2 ^a	\bar{B} -coeff. ^b
NMF	ZnCl ₂	7.2	0.4836	
	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	6.7	1.216	
DMF	NaBr	3.2	0.412	
	KI	1.9	0.526	
	ZnCl ₂	2.7	0.338	
	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	9.2	0.99	
NMA	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	0.4	0.1142	
	NaBr	11.6	0.571	0.885
	KI	6.0	0.715	0.850

^aThe factor $f = 1$ for 1 : 1 electrolytes and $f = 2$ for 2 : 1 electrolytes and used to express fk'/N_0^2 in $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$.

^bP. T. Thompson, P. Durbano, J. L. Turner and R. H. Wood, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1980, 9, 955.

Experimental

DMF, NMF both (E. Merck) and NMA (Fluka) were vacuum distilled in an all-glass apparatus before use. NaBr, KI (Lab Chem. Sarabhai-Merck), ZnCl₂ (Pro Analysi, E. Merck), MgCl₂.6H₂O and Pb(NO₃)₂ (both AnalaR) were used.

The density was measured in a bicapillary pycnometer at 35.0 ± 0.05° in a thermostated water-bath. A set of two suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer was used for viscosity measurement at 35.0 ± 0.05°. The viscometer constants are (1) $A = 5.9908 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S s}^{-1}$, $B = 0.0152 \text{ S s}$ and (2) $A = 5.9713 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S s}^{-1}$, $B = 0.0013 \text{ S s}$. The density and viscosity determined by this method compared favourably with the literature values (Table 3).

Table 3.

Solvent	Density g cm ⁻³	Viscosity P
N-Methylformamide	0.9896 (exptl.)	0.0147 (exptl.)
	0.9898 ^a	0.0146 ^a
N,N-Dimethylformamide	0.9341 (exptl.)	0.007699 (exptl.)
	0.9441 ^b	0.00802 ^b
N-Methylacetamide	0.9460 (exptl.)	0.03468 (exptl.)
	0.9455 ^c	0.03385 ^c
		0.0323 ^d

^aD. Feakins and K. G. Lawrence, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 212.

^bAt 25°; N. C. Dey, G. Kumar, B. K. Saikia and I. Haque, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1985, 14, 49.

^cP. T. Thompson, M. Durbano, J. L. Turner and R. H. Wood, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1980, 9, 955.

^d"Lange's Handbook of Chemistry", ed. J. K. Dean, McGraw Hill, New York, 1985.

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References

- 1 G Jones and M Dole, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1929, **51**, 2950
- 2 C A Angell, *J Phys Chem*, 1966, **70**, 2793, *J Chem Phys*, 1967, **46**, 4673
- 3 K Roy Choudhury and D K Majumdar, *Electrochim Acta*, 1983, **28**, 23
- 4 K Roy Choudhury and D K Majumdar, *Electrochim Acta*, 1983, **28**, 597, D E Goldsack and R C Franchetto, *Can J Chem* 1977, **55**, 1062, 1978, **56**, 1442
- 5 P Haldar and D K Majumdar, *Z Phys Chem (NF)* 1989, **165**, 133
- 6 P Haldar and D K Majumdar, *Z Phys Chem (NF)* 1990, **166**, 183
- 7 P Haldar and D K Majumdar, *Z Phys Chem (NF)* 1990, **167**, 69
- 8 D Balasubramanyam and R Shukla, *Biopolymers* 1973, **12**, 1619
J Bello, D Hass and H R Bello, *J Phys Chem Biochem* 1966 **5**, 2539, B M Rode and R Fussenevgor, *J Chem Soc Faraday Trans 2*, 1975, **71**, 1958, D A Jones and R Mayer, *J Phys Chem*, 1984, **88**, 637